

A Study On Media's Impact On Educational Policies And Practice

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ABSTRACT

This paper looks at the different ways in which media influence educational policies and practice. In order to figure out the media's impact on the educational system, it is also important to understand how educational policies and practices were before the intervention of the media. Additionally, this article explores how media influence people in the educational sector, mainly focusing on students, mentally, emotionally and also in a political sense. An Oxford University study argues that social networking has a bad effect on teen's intelligence. If we look deeper in to it, pandemic scenario, working parents, availability of gadgets, movies portrayed by involving schooling and colleges etc. have an acute influence on peoples' mind. This influence is so profound that it even affects their educational practices, policies and ideologies. The impact can also be seen in terms of moral ethics too. As per UNICEF, children were at increased risk of harm online during global COVID-19 pandemic. By considering current trends and data and also through survey and other media related aspects, this paper takes a look at whether the impact of media enhances or undermines the educational policies and practices.

Keywords: *Social media sites, mobile phones, Internet, Mental and physical health, Influence on youth, Addiction*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Each one of us spends more time in the digital world today and the line between the real world and the virtual world is thinning rapidly. We can say that we are moving practically into a hybrid world where the future will be driven to a great extent by digital technologies. In this scenario, it is important that we and the youth are aware of how to be safe online. The last two years have shown us the rate of adoption of the online world has really accelerated. Now, for a while, online classes and schooling have been a great boon because students were able to continue their education. But in other ways, it also showed that there are some issues out there that we need to get ahead of. All this exposure towards media has a significant consequence on the students' outlook on education system and policies.

In the present context media's influence upon each individual's life is obvious, and it doesn't matter if it is a student or an adult. Additionally, the pandemic scenario has played a significant role in this. In this paper, I would like to focus on students of age ranging from 10 years to 30 years and teachers. It is an attempt to understand how media has transformed the life of students and whether they are aware of its influence upon them. Survey has been done and interpreted, which has yielded alarming results. Those born in early 70s and 80s have been blessed to witness media's growth and were able to get a clear picture on how it took over the world in a very little span of time. One by one, each public and private sector has been under the leverage of social networking sites. But the generation which is raised with technology is not aware of how it affects their perspective towards life, education and attitude.

2.WHAT IS MEDIA:

According to Oxford English Dictionary, ‘media’ refers to “the main means of mass communication, *esp.* Newspapers, radio, and television”. In other words, media refer to the broadcasting or publishing contents through radio, television, internet etc. Social media provides us with all the updates regarding anything in this world. It also plays a vital role in providing justice (example: Nirbhaya case). While defining the word ‘media’ we need to go deeper into the fact that it’s not just something that circulate news or information, but it’s rather a tool that has its influence upon each individual. Most of us rely on these types of media for information, but we have got no clue whether the information we are relying upon is genuine or fake. It’s mainly youngsters or teenagers who trust the social media facts blindly, and it’s really concerning to know that they develop their behavior, attitude etc. from these media sites. It’s important to give a thought to the impacts these media have upon students. Nowadays there are numerous social media sites that are accessible to anyone who wants to get their hands on it. Some popular sites are; Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Snapchat, YouTube, LinkedIn, TikTok, etc.

Here, instead of stating general positives and negatives of social media, I would like to focus upon its influence on students. Because of the COVID situation, students are forced to attend online classes. During lockdown period it was not a matter of concern because parents were at home and children could use their parent’s mobile phones. But once the lockdown period ceased, working parents didn’t have any other option other than providing their kids with new mobile phones. Surveys have clearly stated that more number of students joined social media sites during this period and those who were already using it, their screen time exceeded. Consequence of this is obvious, but also of greater concern. Usage of social media sites by students has bestowed on them with lots of positive aspects. But just like two faces of a coin, it also has its downside too.

The positive effects of social media include the following.

Positive Impacts of Social Media on Students and Education:

- Opportunities For Distant Learning:
- Factual Information/ Content Rich Resources
- Involvement Of Parents
- Improves Communication
- Enhanced Teaching- Learning Process
- Access To Information And Research
- Refines Creativity
- Collaboration
- Source Of Pocket Money
- Platform To Exhibit Talent

Negative Impacts of Social Media on Students and Education

- Addiction
- Health Issues
- Cyberbullying
- Privacy
- Reduces Concentration Power
- Causes Distraction
- Fail To Differentiate Between Fantasy And Reality
- Reduces Learning And Research Capabilities
- Tends To Abuse And Misuse Their Skills
- Fails To Implement Discipline In Their Life
- Tends To Spend More Money
- Inability To Think Independently
- Self Esteem Issue

➤ Affects Communication And Writing Skills

3.RESEARCH DESIGN:

Since this particular paper focuses on the life of a student in a world which is taken over by social media sites, the experience of each individual varies from person to person. So in order to undergo fact based analysis, quantitative method is used. A Survey has been done in a questionnaire form for students ranging from 10 to 30 years of age. Response from 340 students has been analyzed and insights were derived based on the data collected. Most of the responses were from the age range of 15-20. The data that was collected did not have any personal information such as their name, native or educational institution they study or their parental details. Yet, it can be told that most of the students whose insights were collected are from Kasaragod, Mangalore and Trivandrum.

Here are the survey questions and the answers received.

1. Which age category you belong to?

2. What is your gender?

3. Your current educational status.

4. Do you use your own mobile phone?

5. Which of the media platforms do you use?

6. Do you use social media to communicate with your teachers?

Communicate with teacher

7. Do you use social media to communicate with your teachers?

Social media in life

8. How much time do you spend on social media sites in a day?

Time Spent

9. How much time do you spend on social media sites in a day?

10. What do you prefer to see in social media?

11. At what times are you most active in social media?

12. Do you keep track about your number of followers in social media sites?

13. In your opinion how does the usage of social media affect your academics?

14. Do you think the pandemic situation has increased your social media usage?

15. Have your ever felt after being introduced to social networking site made you lazy?

16. What has happened to your productivity after being introduced to social sites?

17. Has the usage of social networking sites benefitted your studies?

18. If yes, in what all ways?

19. What in your opinion are the challenges of using social media sites?

20. Do you visit social media sites during online classes?

21. Would you be able to stay away from all the social media sites for at least one week?

4.ANALYSIS:

From the data collected, we can infer that most of them who responded to this survey were female and of age between 10 and 20. It is also shown that most of them of this age own their mobile phones and use almost all social media platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram etc. where WhatsApp and Instagram holds the first place among all these, i.e., 88.1% and 78.57% respectively. Those who don't own mobile have also responded by saying that they too wish to have, but parents don't allow them to have it. From this it's very clear that there are parents who are worried about their children owning a cellphone and are well aware of the challenges it poses. It is inferred that 3% of the students use all types of gadgets for social media usage, and they don't depend upon mobile phone alone. So even if the child doesn't own a mobile phone still he/she can access the sites if there is Wi-Fi and other gadgets like tablet, computer etc. at home. Almost 85% of the students use social media sites to communicate with their teachers. It's a revealing truth that no one considers social media platforms just as an educational tool, instead 90% of students find it useful for both educational and entertainment tools. Here the issue rises is that the kind of entertainment that they are referring to. It's obvious that entertainment preferences changes from person to person, and it is where most of the teenagers and youngsters fail to draw the line and falls in to the trap.

It is acknowledged that about 42% of the students spend their time in social media sites for more than 3 hours a day and that too it's spent after 7 pm by almost 95%. Likewise, it points the finger upon the various health issues that can be caused due to continuous usage of gadgets and can also lead to serious addiction. Many of them are concerned about the followers they have in social media and try hard to increase the number. It's noticed that 17% are really concerned regarding the number of followers and about 19.5% make an effort to increase this number. While reading between the lines the reason for social

media addiction becomes obvious.

From the survey, we can also perceive that about 85.71% of them prefer to use social media sites for watching videos. It includes various platforms like YouTube Instagram, Facebook, etc. Here the discussion stretches out to one of the most trending site we had until last year, TikTok. Many talents have been exhibited through this particular application and have also helped a lot to come in front of the screen and got recognized and appreciated by everyone. Around 57.5% agrees that the media has a good impact on their academics too and has benefitted their studies. 64.8% agrees to the fact that social media usage has helped them to learn new digital literacy skills and about 51.85% of them revealed that it has also improved their language skills. But the sad part is that most of them fail to acknowledge the negatives that come along with all these positives. Only 20% gives social media being a bad impact in their academics and about 22.5% gives a neutral response, social media being both good and bad. The major concerns that are aroused by these applications are privacy concern, cyberbullying, self-obsession, addiction, etc.

74.14% of students agree to the fact that after being introduced to social media sites has made them lazier than ever and about 48% of them admit that social networking sites have decreased their productivity. But it is relieving to find that majority of them accept that social sites raise so many challenges. 61.4% claims that introduction of social media sites has decreased face-to-face communication skills and 59% agrees to the addiction part of media as well.

Moreover, it is also observed that 58.62% of the students often visit other social media sites during online classes. Here, it contradicts their positive response regarding good impact of social media on academics. It evidently shows the lack of concentration they have. Everyone, i.e. 96.5% of students, realize that it is after the pandemic situation their social media usage has increased and about 67% admits that they can never abstain from the social networking sites.

In addition to all these, there are matter of moral ethics and development of attitudes and behavior that are being influenced largely by the media. For instance, there are mass media videos/ movies which portray the relationship between a teacher and students in a worse way, like the Malayalam movie *Premam*, Netflix movie *The Lust Stories* etc. All these give a bad impression on students regarding their relationship with the teacher. Instead of valuing and respecting the one who educates them to be a better person in future is often viewed in a worse way.

Furthermore, there are so many movies which give a wrong image regarding college life. For instance, films such as *Anandam*, *Student of the Year*, *Rang de Basanti*, *KuchkuchHotahai*, *Main Hoon Na*, *Mohabbatein*, etc. After watching movies like this, most of them expect college life to be like this and instead of focusing on studies and career, they end up trying to make all the fantasies true and become disappointed. Additionally, the smoking and drinking creates a false imagery on youngsters. Kelvin Choi in his article, *The Reciprocal Relationships Between Changes in Adolescent Perceived Prevalence of Smoking in Movies and Progression of Smoking Status*, points out that about 85% of teenagers ranges from 16 to 20 years of recalls that actors and actresses smoking in particular scenes. His findings proved that with the decline in smoking scenes in movies, teenager's impression on smoking has also declined. In her article, *Impacts of Films: Changes in Young People's Attitudes after watching a movie*, Tina Kubarak talks about negative attitude towards elderly people which shows the bad influence of film on the students.

5.SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION:

All the surveys and studies put forward the fact that even though exposure to media provides lots of advantages to student life, the negative threats posed by it cannot be neglected. Although from the survey conducted, students seem to be aware of the negative threats, yet it cannot be implied that all of them will be cautious enough to stay away from that. Every nook and corner of the social networking site can be threatening to anyone who gets their hands on it.

Digital world can be addictive, and that addiction can be detrimental to student's health. There are documented correlations between extended use of technology and physical and psychological issues, including mental stress, eye problems, ergonomic issues, etc. We exist online, just as we exist in the physical world. Dangers exist in both physical and online world. Hence, we must exert the same level of caution online as we do offline. The only preventive measure we can hold on to is to make everyone aware of 'digital citizenship'. In the article *Digital citizenship and its teaching: A literature review*, by

GulcanOzturk quotes the definition of digital citizen from Ranchordas's article *We teach and learn online. Are we all digital citizens now? Lessons on Digital Citizenship from the Lockdown* and according to him "the rules for correct and responsible technology usage that provide guidance to students on how to direct the online world in their personal and academic lives rather than just being a citizen of a country are called digital citizenship" (Parent and Community Impact, Technology, 2018; Ranchordas, 2020; Tan, 2011). Teaching digital citizenship equips students to learn about digital world and engage it with responsibility and confidence. Digital citizenship often takes care of the components like;

- Digital Etiquette
- Prevention of Cyberbullying
- Online safety
- Information Literacy
- Digital Footprint
- Health and Emotional Wellness
- Parent and Teacher Toolkit

Students should be taught to protect themselves and their identities by visiting appropriate websites, refraining from posting personal information and notifying trusted adult when things don't feel right. Students who are aware of these things feel confident about taking control of their digital lives are less susceptible to potential online threats.

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